

Identification of a Previously Uncatalogued Extended Dust Cloud Candidate in Aquila, Associated with IRAS 19448–0234

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Abstract

I report the identification of an extended cold dust cloud candidate at Galactic coordinates $l \approx 37.2^\circ$, $b \approx -13.6^\circ$ (J2000: RA $19^h 47^m 30^s$, Dec $-02^\circ 27' 07''$). The structure, measuring approximately $20' \times 15'$ in angular extent, is consistently visible across six independent surveys spanning optical to far-infrared wavelengths: DSS2, PanSTARRS, AllWISE, AKARI FIS, IRAS-IRIS, and my own deep optical imaging. The AKARI FIS far-infrared emission is spatially superimposable on the optical structure, supporting morphological coherence between optical extinction and far-infrared thermal emission. A catalogued far-infrared point source, IRAS 19448–0234, is identified here as the compact emission core of this extended structure. The far-infrared flux pattern of IRAS 19448–0234, combining IRAS and AKARI FIS photometry, is diagnostic of cold quiescent dust with no embedded heating source. A modified blackbody fit to the available far-infrared photometry (IRAS + AKARI FIS) yields a dust temperature of $T_{\text{dust}} = 29.0 + 2.6/-2.1$ K (at $\beta = 1.8$), consistent with a diffuse or translucent cloud heated by the ambient interstellar radiation field with no embedded heating source. The Bayestar 2019 3D dust extinction map indicates a distance of about 200 pc, which establishes a physical size of 1.2×0.9 pc, at about 47 pc below the Galactic plane. An HI 21cm spectrum from the HI4PI survey shows cold atomic gas at $V_{\text{LSR}} = +2.7$ km/s, with a column density consistent with the measured dust extinction, suggesting a predominantly atomic structure. The Dame & Thaddeus (2022) all-sky CO survey shows no CO emission from the cloud. The precise gas content of this structure — whether a CO-dark molecular cloud, a translucent cloud, or cold diffuse cirrus — cannot be determined from the available data alone. Pointed CO spectroscopy is encouraged to search for molecular gas.

1. Introduction

The field at $l = 37.2^\circ$, $b = -13.6^\circ$ lies in the general direction of the Aquila constellation at intermediate Galactic latitude, well outside the Galactic plane. At $|b| = 13.6^\circ$, this position lies beyond the formal coverage boundaries of major Galactic plane surveys, including the Galactic Ring Survey (GRS; $|b| < 1^\circ$; Jackson et al. 2006), ATLASGAL ($|b| \leq 1.5^\circ$; Schuller et al. 2009), and Hi-GAL ($|b| \leq 1^\circ$; Molinari et al. 2010), creating a systematic gap in the molecular cloud census at these latitudes. Intermediate Galactic latitude clouds form a distinct population of the cold ISM (Magnani et al. 1985).

During deep optical imaging of this intermediate Galactic latitude field, I identified an extended $20' \times 15'$ structure, visible in both optical extinction and far-infrared thermal emission, consistent across multiple independent survey datasets. A search of major molecular cloud catalogs — including the Planck Galactic Cold Clumps catalog (PGCC; Planck Collaboration 2016), SIMBAD, VizieR, and the Milky Way molecular cloud databases — reveals no prior classification of this structure as a molecular cloud or cloud candidate. The only catalog entry

at this position is IRAS 19448–0234, a far-infrared point source detected by the *IRAS* satellite in 1983 and listed in the *IRAS* catalog (Beichman et al. 1988) with no subsequent published follow-up.

This work represents the first multi-wavelength characterisation of this object, combining original deep optical imaging with archival data from several survey instruments. Importantly, a modified blackbody SED fit indicates a temperature consistent with a cold dust cloud (Testi 2026). Here, in addition, I calculate the approximate distance, relation to the Galactic plane, size, velocity and HI emission of the cloud.

2. Observations and Archival Data

2.1 Deep Optical Imaging

Deep optical imaging of the field was obtained by the author. Imaging was performed with a f/7 refractor (William Optics Fluorostar 132 / FLT132) and one-shot color camera (ZWO ASI2600 MC Pro), yielding a pixel scale of 1.088 arcsec/pixel and a FOV of 88 x 58 arcmin, on an iOptron CEM70EC center balance equatorial mount. A total of 147 guided sub-exposures of 10 min each (total of 24h 30') were acquired through an Optolong L-Quad Enhance filter, between July 22 and 30, 2025, from a Bortle 4.5 location, at an average of about 16% moon phase. Calibration frames were applied and frames were stacked using Siril software. Final processing was performed with Siril and PixInsight software. The processed image was published by the author on the Astrobin platform on August 9, 2025. The image reveals a faint but morphologically distinct nebular structure measuring approximately 20' x 15', consistent with dust scattering or extinction against the background stellar field.

2.2 Archival Survey Data

To confirm the reality of the structure and characterise its spectral properties, I examined archival data from the following surveys at the coordinates of the detected structure:

Survey	Wavelength	Angular Resolution	Detection
DSS2 (blue, red)	Optical	~2"	Dust extinction; cloud outline visible
PanSTARRS	Optical	~1"	Consistent morphology with DSS2
AllWISE (W1, W2, W4)	3.4–22 μm	~6 - 12"	Mid-IR emission, consistent extent
AKARI FIS	65–160 μm	~37 - 61"	Far-IR emission superimposable on optical
IRAS-IRIS	60–100 μm	~4 - 5'	Extended, major axis aligned with optical

All survey data were examined using Aladin Sky Atlas (Bonnarel et al. 2000) with appropriate image stretching. No additional catalog entries or published objects were identified within 12' of the cloud centroid beyond the IRAS 19448–0234 entry.

3. Multi-Wavelength Morphology

The structure is detected consistently in all six survey datasets examined (Fig 1). At optical wavelengths (DSS2 red, DSS2 blue, PanSTARRS), the cloud appears as a region of enhanced extinction against the background stellar field, with a coherent morphology measuring approximately $20' \times 15'$. The AllWISE colour composite (W1 $3.4 \mu\text{m}$, W2 $4.6 \mu\text{m}$, W4 $22 \mu\text{m}$) shows emission with spatial extent consistent with the optical structure; the W1 and W2 channels primarily trace stellar photospheres, while any dust contribution appears in the W4 band at $22 \mu\text{m}$.

Most significantly, the AKARI FIS far-infrared emission, shown as a three-band composite (N60 $65 \mu\text{m}$, WIDE-S $90 \mu\text{m}$, WIDE-L $140 \mu\text{m}$), is spatially superimposable on the optical structure visible in my deep imaging and in DSS2. This morphological coherence between optical extinction and far-infrared thermal emission across instruments with fundamentally different detection principles and angular resolutions constitutes strong evidence that the optical and far-infrared signals arise from a single, physically coherent dust structure, rather than a chance superposition of unrelated objects along the line of sight.

At the coarser resolution of the IRAS-IRIS (Improved Reprocessing of the IRAS Survey, Miville-Deschênes, M.-A. & Lagache, G. 2005) maps ($\sim 1.5'/\text{pixel}$), the emission appears extended with a major axis orientation consistent with that of the optical cloud, providing additional corroboration at a third angular resolution.

The cloud exhibits a distinctly asymmetric morphology, with a compact bright condensation at its lower end and diffuse extended emission trailing toward the upper portion of the field. This structure is consistent with a cometary or ablated cloud morphology, in which the denser leading edge is compressed by ram pressure and lower-density material is stripped into a trailing wake. The dense end of the cloud is oriented toward lower Galactic latitudes, consistent with infall toward the Galactic plane.

An alternative interpretation is that the cloud elongation reflects alignment with the local interstellar magnetic field. Cold ISM clouds are known to align preferentially with their local magnetic field (e.g. Clark et al. 2014), and without polarisation measurements the field orientation at this position is unknown, making this interpretation impossible to exclude.

4. Association with IRAS 19448–0234

The catalogued IRAS source IRAS 19448–0234 (Beichman et al. 1988) lies at the nominal position of the extended structure. In the IRAS Sky Survey Atlas, the source appears point-like, unresolved within the IRAS beam ($\sim 4'–5'$ FWHM at $100 \mu\text{m}$). The reported positional uncertainty ellipse (semi-major axis $72''$, semi-minor axis $3''$, PA = 59°) is characteristic of the IRAS scan geometry and does not reflect source extent. The extended $20' \times 15'$ cloud structure identified here therefore represents spatial information not recoverable from the IRAS data alone.

SIMBAD classifies IRAS 19448–0234 as a far-infrared source ($> 30 \mu\text{m}$) with a single bibliographic reference to the 1988 IRAS catalog. No subsequent paper has discussed, classified, or followed up this source in over 40 years of literature. Therefore, IRAS 19448–0234 most likely represents the compact far-infrared emission core of the extended cloud structure reported here.

5. Far-Infrared Photometry, SED, Distance and Gas Content

5.1 Photometry

Flux densities for IRAS 19448–0234 were retrieved from the *IRAS* Faint Source Catalog (FSC; Moshir et al. 1990) and the AKARI FIS Bright Source Catalog (Yamamura et al. 2010) via the Vizier service. The highest-confidence detections are the IRAS 100 μm flux (5.27 ± 0.30 Jy, $q = 3$) and the AKARI S140 flux (4.36 ± 0.42 Jy, $q = 3$), which anchor the modified blackbody fit described in Section 5.2. The Table below summarises the available photometry.

Band	Wavelength (μm)	Flux density (Jy)	Quality
IRAS 12	12	< 2.50	Upper limit
IRAS 25	25	< 2.50	Upper limit
IRAS 60	60	< 4.08	Upper limit
AKARI S65	65	Not detected	Non-detection
AKARI S90	90	3.66 ± 2.37	Marginal ($q=1$)
IRAS 100	100	5.27 ± 0.30	Solid ($q=3$)
AKARI S140	140	4.36 ± 0.42	Solid ($q=3$)
AKARI S160	160	4.05 ± 2.15	Marginal ($q=1$)

5.2 Modified Blackbody Fit

The SED shows a clear cold dust signature: no detections shortward of 90 μm , a solid detection at 100 μm (5.27 Jy), and declining flux at longer wavelengths. This pattern is inconsistent with the presence of a warm embedded source (which would produce significant 12–25 μm emission) and is consistent with cold, quiescent dust heated by the ambient interstellar radiation field.

A modified blackbody function $S(\nu) \propto \nu^\beta \times B(\nu, T)$ was fitted to the available photometry detections using a χ^2 minimisation over dust temperature with an analytic normalisation optimisation. All detections were weighted by their catalogue uncertainties. Adopting a dust emissivity spectral index $\beta = 1.8$, consistent with standard ISM dust properties (Planck Collaboration 2011), I obtain:

$$T_{\text{dust}} = 29.0 +2.6/-2.1 \text{ K} \quad (1\sigma)$$

The derived dust temperature of ~ 29 K is characteristic of a diffuse or translucent cloud heated externally by the interstellar radiation field, consistent with the absence of internal short-wavelength emission and with the intermediate Galactic latitude environment where the interstellar radiation field heats the dust externally (Fig. 2). This temperature is warmer than deeply embedded starless dark cores (~ 10 – 15 K) but cooler than clouds with active embedded sources (> 40 K), placing this object in the temperature regime of diffuse or translucent ISM clouds.

5.3 Distance and Physical Size

A distance estimate is obtained from the Bayestar 2019 three-dimensional dust extinction map (Green et al. 2019), which models stellar photometry from Pan-STARRS, 2MASS and Gaia to

produce a probabilistic map of dust reddening as a function of distance across the sky. Two independent query methods were used (Fig. 3). First, the reddening profile was extracted using the `dustmaps` Python package (Green 2018) at the cloud coordinates ($l = 37.20^\circ$, $b = -13.58^\circ$) with a 0.5° beam. The cumulative $E(B-V)$ profile shows a sharp onset at ~ 200 pc, with no reddening detected at shorter distances, and a peak in the derivative $dE(B-V)/dd$ at the same distance, identifying the cloud front. Second, an independent extraction via the Argonaut web interface (`argonaut.skymaps.info`) at the same coordinates yields a best-fit distance of $d = 0.22$ kpc, with a reddening of $E(g-r) = 0.04 +0.05/-0.03$ mag attributed to the cloud. Both methods consistently indicate a cloud distance of ~ 200 – 220 pc. At $d \approx 200$ pc the cloud has a physical size of approximately 1.2×0.9 pc and lies ~ 47 pc below the Galactic plane ($z = d \times \sin|b| = 200 \text{ pc} \times \sin(13.6^\circ) \approx 47 \text{ pc}$), consistent with membership of the local ISM. The line-of-sight depth cannot be constrained at this distance due to the ~ 50 – 80 pc distance resolution of the Bayestar map at 200 pc, but is assumed comparable to the transverse dimensions based on the compact morphology of the cloud.

5.4 HI 21cm Emission

An HI 21cm spectrum extracted from the HI4PI all-sky survey (HI4PI Collaboration 2016) at the cloud position using the Effelsberg-Bonn HI Survey (EBHIS) data (0.5° beam) shows a prominent emission component at $V_{\text{LSR}} = +2.7$ km/s, with a peak brightness temperature of 42.8 K and FWHM ≈ 4.4 km/s (Fig. 4). The total HI column density along this sightline is $N(\text{HI}) = 7.5 \times 10^{20} \text{ cm}^{-2}$ (EBHIS). This is in good agreement with the value predicted from the Bayestar reddening measurement ($E(B-V) \approx 0.11$ mag) using the standard dust-to-gas ratio $N(\text{HI})/E(B-V) \approx 5.8 \times 10^{21} \text{ cm}^{-2} \text{ mag}^{-1}$ (Bohlin et al. 1978), which yields $N(\text{HI}) \approx 6.4 \times 10^{20} \text{ cm}^{-2}$. A secondary emission component is visible at $V_{\text{LSR}} \approx +20$ km/s (Fig. 4), kinematically distinct from the main component and consistent with background HI at a greater distance along the same line of sight, not associated with the cloud.

The consistency between the measured and predicted HI column densities suggests the dust and gas are physically associated and that the cloud is predominantly in the atomic rather than molecular phase. The low LSR velocity ($+2.7$ km/s) is consistent with the photometric distance estimate of ~ 200 pc. Note that the brightness temperature T_B is a radio astronomy convention expressing signal intensity in Kelvin via the Rayleigh-Jeans approximation, and is unrelated to the dust temperature derived from the SED fit. The HI line width (FWHM ≈ 4.4 km/s) implies a kinetic temperature of the gas of ~ 280 K, characteristic of the Cold Neutral Medium (CNM). However, a direct quantitative comparison of $N(\text{HI})$ with the dust reddening is complicated by beam size differences: the HI4PI extraction uses a 0.5° beam averaging over a larger area, while the Bayestar Argonaut point-source estimate attributes $E(g-r) = 0.04$ mag to the cloud specifically. The consistency between the HI column density and the dust extinction is therefore indicative rather than precise.

6. Discussion

6.1 Why Was This Cloud Not Previously Catalogued?

The non-cataloguing of this cloud in major molecular cloud databases can be attributed to a combination of factors. Its Galactic latitude ($b = -13.6^\circ$) places it just outside the formal latitude boundaries of many key surveys: the GRS covers $|b| < 1^\circ$, ATLASGAL covers $|b| \leq 1.5^\circ$, and the Hi-GAL survey covers $|b| \leq 1^\circ$. The cloud therefore falls in a systematic coverage gap of the existing molecular cloud census at intermediate Galactic latitude. A search of the Dame & Thaddeus all-sky CO survey (Dame & Thaddeus 2022), while covering the area, yields no detection at the cloud position (Fig. 5). This is consistent with the intermediate Galactic latitude

environment, where enhanced UV flux may photodissociate CO while leaving H₂ intact — so-called CO-dark molecular gas (Wolfire et al. 2010).

6.2 Need for Radio Follow-Up

The HI4PI spectrum shows cold atomic gas at $V_{\text{LSR}} = +2.7$ km/s, consistent with the photometric distance, and the $N(\text{HI})/E(\text{B}-\text{V})$ ratio is consistent with a predominantly atomic cloud. However, the Dame & Thaddeus all-sky CO survey (Dame & Thaddeus 2022) has limited sensitivity ($\sim 0.1\text{--}0.2$ K) and a non-detection does not rule out faint molecular gas below this threshold. CO-dark H₂ — molecular gas in regions where CO is photodissociated by UV radiation but H₂ survives through self-shielding — is estimated to constitute 30–50% of all molecular hydrogen in the Milky Way (Wolfire et al. 2010), particularly at cloud edges and in environments with significant UV fields such as intermediate Galactic latitudes. Direct detection of CO-dark H₂ requires tracers such as [CII] 158 μm emission or gamma-ray emissivity measurements, neither of which is currently available for this object. Until such observations are available, the object is most conservatively classified as a cold dust cloud candidate, predominantly atomic in character based on the available HI and dust data.

6.3 Possible Evolution

The cloud's column density of $N(\text{HI}) = 7.5 \times 10^{20}$ cm⁻² is below the typical threshold of $\sim 2 \times 10^{21}$ cm⁻² required for effective H₂ self-shielding (Hollenbach & Tielens 1999), suggesting it has not yet accumulated sufficient column density for significant molecular formation. Its future evolution — whether toward a molecular cloud or dispersal into the diffuse ISM — depends on its vertical velocity relative to the Galactic plane and the likelihood of compression by external events, neither of which is currently constrained.

The asymmetric morphology of the cloud, with its compact bright condensation oriented toward lower Galactic latitudes, is suggestive of infall dynamics. At $z = -47$ pc and with a near-zero radial velocity ($V_{\text{LSR}} = +2.7$ km/s), the bulk of any infall velocity would appear as transverse motion undetectable with current data. If the cloud is infalling with velocities typical of Galactic fountain return flows (10–50 km/s; Putman et al. 2012), it would reach the midplane in approximately 5–20 Myr, where compression by the higher-pressure midplane environment could potentially trigger a transition toward molecular cloud formation. However, the actual infall velocity is not directly constrained by the available data, and an alternative interpretation — that the cloud elongation reflects alignment with the local interstellar magnetic field — cannot be excluded.

7. Conclusions

I have identified an extended 20' \times 15' dust cloud candidate at RA 19^h 47^m 30^s, Dec -02°27' 07" (J2000; $l \approx 37.2^\circ$, $b \approx -13.6^\circ$), consistently detected across six independent survey datasets from optical to far-infrared wavelengths. The principal findings are as follows:

- (1) The cold dust emission traced by AKARI FIS is spatially superimposable on the optical extinction structure across all survey datasets, demonstrating physical coherence of the object. The catalogued source IRAS 19448-0234 (Beichman et al. 1988) is identified here for the first time as the compact far-infrared emission core associated with this extended structure.
- (2) The far-infrared SED shows no emission shortward of 90 μm , with a modified blackbody fit yielding $T_{\text{pUts}} \approx 29.0$ K ($\beta = 1.8$), diagnostic of cold quiescent dust with no embedded heating source.

(3) Estimate of the distance and size places this object at about 200 pc from us and about 47 pc below the Galactic plane, with a size of about 1.2×0.9 pc, placing it within the local ISM.

(4) An HI 21cm spectrum from the HI4PI survey shows cold atomic gas at $V_{\text{LSR}} = +2.7$ km/s with $N(\text{HI}) = 7.5 \times 10^{20} \text{ cm}^{-2}$, consistent with the photometric distance and suggesting the cloud is predominantly atomic in character.

(5) No CO emission is detected in the Dame & Thaddeus (2022) survey, consistent with a CO-dark, CO-faint, or purely atomic structure.

Pointed CO J=1–0 spectroscopy is strongly encouraged to determine whether molecular gas is present below the Dame & Thaddeus (2022) survey detection threshold.

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